

Using NOMA for Enabling Broadcast/Unicast Convergence in 5G Networks

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Abstract— The coexistence of broadcast and unicast services has always been a technological challenge. Now, this concept has arisen again from the standardization process of 5G. Although the latest 5G Release has not defined any broadcast capability, it is expected to be included in the near future (Rel' 17/18). Therefore, new solutions for an optimum service convergence have to be designed and developed. In this paper, a solution for Broadcast/Broadband convergence in 5G networks based on Power-based Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access (P-NOMA) is presented and tested. In order to test the proposed solution, first a PHY/MAC level transceiver prototype has been developed. Moreover, the implications and the benefits of the presented solution are detailed. Then, the P-NOMA-based 5G proposal has been implemented in a network simulator. The results obtained in terms of capacity and reliability demonstrate that the proposed solution is able to offer a proper broadcast/unicast convergence by enhancing the overall system performance.

Index Terms—5G, Broadcast, Convergence, LDM, MAC, NOMA, P-NOMA, Unicast.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE standardization process required to create and enhance the fifth generation of mobile communications (5G), which is expected to cover all the increasing connectivity necessities [1], is ongoing. In fact, the first Release (Rel' 15) of 5G New Radio (NR) has already been published [2] and several improvements in different levels of the protocol stack make this solution a proper alternative for different use cases. One of the most relevant contributions can be considered the introduction of LDPC codes (Low-Density Parity-Check) in order to enhance the communication reliability. It should also be mentioned the development of a flexible Physical Layer (PHY) that can be implemented in several scenarios with completely different requirements.

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Fig. 1. 5G NR applications and use case families [3].

Taking into account this standardization process, the Radiocommunication Sector of the International Telecommunication Union (ITU-R) has divided the entire application frame into three use case families: Enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB), Ultra Reliable Low Latency Communications (URLLC) and Massive Machine Type Communications (mMTC) [3]. In Fig. 1, a summary of the use case families is shown with some other more specific applications.

Each one of the different verticals shown in Fig. 1 has different requirements. In eMBB, for instance, which is related to the classic information and entertainment media delivery scenario, high data rates are required. In fact, it is expected to guarantee peak data rate values close to 10-20 Gbps and support high mobility rates up to 500 km/h. In the case of URLLC, as it is oriented to mission-critical communications, reliability and latency are the most demanded requirements. In fact, an upper bound of one millisecond of end-to-end latency has been established. Finally, concerning mMTC, the network is expected to increase the device density rate to values close to 10^6 devices per km^2 and increase the battery lifetime around 10 years.

The combination of the large list of new applications and the configuration flexibility presented in the latest Release gives the opportunity to become 5G the main generic solution for wireless communications. However, a mechanism that could enhance the 5G performance is still missing: Point-to-Multipoint (PTM) communications. Although it is true that

broadcast/multicast communications are not considered in this first version, there will probably be integrated in future Releases (Rel'17/18).

Once a mechanism to integrate PTM communications is integrated, there will be still other open issues, for instance, the convergence between unicast/broadcast services. Traditionally, in 4G systems, eMBMS (Evolved Multimedia Broadcast Multicast Services) has been implemented, which is based on Time Division Multiplexing (TDM) and could be complemented with Frequency Division Multiplexing (FDM).

This paper proposes a different standpoint to replace or to complement eMBMS: NOMA techniques.

As described in [4], a layered division or power-based NOMA can be implemented in order to deliver simultaneously different services assuming diverse power levels and configurations. The main advantage of P-NOMA systems is that the 100% of the RF bandwidth is used during the 100% of time to transmit two (or more) services. That is why, NOMA is considered a spectral efficiency friendly technique, when compared with classical solutions, such as TDM or FDM.

In addition to that, the principal example of the success of P-NOMA systems is the acceptance of a low complexity P-NOMA structure, Layered Division Multiplexing (LDM), to be part of the ATSC 3.0 PHY layer baseline technology [5]. In this case, a robust configuration is implemented in the Upper Layer (UL) oriented to portable and mobile receivers. On the other hand, in the Lower Layer (LL) a high capacity configuration is chosen to deliver high data rate services to fix terminals, such as UHD TV or multiple HDTV services.

The main objective of this paper is to propose, design and evaluate a novel solution for enabling broadcast/unicast service convergence in 5G networks based on P-NOMA. Afterwards, the main implications of this architecture are presented as well as the solutions that have been implemented. Finally, the prototype is evaluated at PHY level using an upgraded network simulation tool. PHY and network level results are shown and analyzed, separately.

In summary, the technical contributions of this paper include:

- 1) Full integration of non-orthogonal multiplexing techniques in 5G NR at PHY/MAC level.
- 2) Design and implementation of a frame adaptation layer to combine UL and LL MAC packets.
- 3) Novel proposal for using P-NOMA to guarantee broadcast/unicast convergence.
- 4) Threshold and gain analysis of the proposed technique over different propagation channels.
- 5) Presentation of network level simulations and reliability, latency and capacity analysis.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. The next section describes the related work published up to now in this topic. Section III is focused on the overview of the 5G NR at different levels. In section IV, the NOMA-based 5G model is

presented, taking into account the implications and the proposed novelties. Then, in section V, a PHY level evaluation of the proposed solution is carried out. In section VI, the proposed solution is tested in a network simulation tool. Finally, section VII contains the future works and section VIII the conclusions.

II. RELATED WORK

A. Broadcast/Unicast convergence

5G is expected to be the global solution to guarantee convergence and cooperation between different networks, devices and technologies. However, in its first version, Release 15, a fundamental scenario, especially for eMBB communications, has not been considered: PTM or broadcast content distribution.

The broadcast implementation roadmap in 5G has similar milestones if compared to its predecessor, 4G. Although a broadcast traffic distribution alternative was already included in the previous 3G systems (Multimedia Broadcast Multicast Services, MBMS), it was not included in the first LTE version. It was not until Release 9 that the first broadcast transmission capabilities were introduced. In fact, in 4G, a slightly enhanced solution was presented (evolved MBMS, eMBMS), which brought higher and more flexible bit rates, single frequency network (SFN) operations and carrier configuration flexibility [6]. Latest enhancements applied to eMBMS were included in LTE Release 14. One of the most relevant differences was that the limitation of the maximum of 60% of radio resources for broadcast transmissions was removed [7].

Concerning the future of broadcast in 5G, the most relevant contributions are related to the 5G-Xcast project [8]. 5G-Xcast was an international research project, funded by the European Commission (EC) that started in June 2017. This project presented a cross-layer proposal at different architecture levels. Among other issues, in [9], a specific approach of the 5G NR PHY for terrestrial broadcast is presented. In this paper, the critical parameters of the waveform generation are discussed and the NR-based MBMS solution is compared with the latest LTE Release 14 version. Aiming to cover a different perspective, in [10], the network slicing concept is discussed within the 5G paradigm. In fact, the main implications are detailed in order to optimize the network resources of a particular 5G infrastructure over different use cases.

B. NOMA for 5G systems

NOMA-based systems such as LDM, have demonstrated very positive properties and an excellent performance for broadcast applications. Nevertheless, it is still not considered for broadband communication systems. In fact, NOMA solutions were not included in 4G, but several works presented it as a relevant candidate for broadcasting in 5G.

TABLE I
5G NR SUBCARRIER SPACING INFLUENCE

μ	SCS (kHz)	# Slots/Subframe	Slot (ms)
0	15	1	1
1	30	2	0.5
2	60	4	0.25
3	120	8	0.125
4	240	16	0.0625

TABLE II
OFDM SYMBOLS

	$\mu = 0$	$\mu = 1$	$\mu = 2$	$\mu = 3$	$\mu = 4$
OFDM Symbol (μ s)	66.67	33.33	16.67	8.33	4.17
CP (μ s)	4.69	2.34	1.17	0.57	0.29
Total length (μ s)	71.36	35.67	17.84	8.90	4.46

TABLE III
RESOURCE BLOCKS AND BANDWIDTH SIZES

μ	RB _{MIN}	RB _{MAX}	BW _{MIN}	BW _{MAX}
0	24	275	4.32	49.5
1	24	275	8.64	99
2	24	275	17.28	198
3	24	275	34.56	396
4	24	138	69.12	397.44

One of the first works that evaluated the use of NOMA within eMBMS is [11]. In this paper, several scenarios where the efficiency increase of LDM would be profitable are presented and the theoretical Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) thresholds for different injection level values are provided. Some other works evaluated the interoperability of NOMA systems with the eMBMS ecosystem based on LTE or theoretical 5G approaches [12][13]. While [12] studies the use of NOMA as a key technology for 5G networks to deliver PTM transmission within the broadband systems, the authors in [13] present NOMA as a candidate to carry out multicast transmissions in subgroup oriented communications.

Concerning non-theoretical contributions, in [14], the transmission of unicast and broadcast services at the same time in a single frequency network (SFN) by using LDM are analyzed. In this case, the study is based on measuring the power consumption per base station. Finally, in [15], the first NOMA-based 5G NR PHY layer transceiver was presented. The prototype was tested by implemented a convergence-oriented use case. Results offer significant capacity gains in different configurations. However, the AWGN channel was the only simulation case and the impact of retransmissions (HARQ) were not evaluated.

III. 5G OVERVIEW

As in the previous version, 5G PHY is based on the popular Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing (OFDM) technique. However, one of the main novelties of this standard is not the base technology, but its configuration flexibility.

There are five different numerologies (μ) available with different subcarrier spacing (SCS) values. Those values are obtained from the following expression:

$$SCS (kHz) = 15 \cdot 2^\mu \quad (1)$$

Fig. 2. Basic resource management terminologies

where μ can be 0, 1, 2, 3 or 4.

In 5G NR, each radio frame has a fixed length of 10ms and it is composed of a fixed number of ten subframes. Moreover, each subframe has a duration of one millisecond. The number of slots per subframe varies depending on the numerology that is implemented. In TABLE I, a summary of the possible number of slots per subframes and their duration is presented as a function of the SCS. In comparison with previous standards, this aspect is considered a relevant difference. In addition, the number of OFDM symbols per slot is also configurable. Although the default number of symbols per slot is 14, different configurations can be implemented. On the one hand, in order to enable the transmission of short data packet, a mini-slot configuration has been introduced in the standard, where 2, 4 or 7 symbols can be allocated. On the other hand, just with the opposite aim, slots can be gathered for longer transmissions.

Another variable that can be tuned is the OFDM symbol length. TABLE II presents the OFDM symbol lengths with and without the Cyclic Prefix (CP). As shown, the shortest OFDM symbol lengths allow their transmission in less than 5 μ s. In consequence, the highest numerologies, especially $\mu = 3$ and $\mu = 4$, are designed for URLLC, due to their short airtime.

Finally, the main PHY level novelty from the reliability point of view is the new channel coding. In fact, 5G NR does not include Turbo-codes; LDPC and Polar codes are supported. Polar codes are reserved for control packet transmissions and LDPC codes are used in payload data packets. Indeed, LDPC codes have demonstrated to be a very robust channel coding technique and their reliability is very close to the Shannon limit, just half a dB away [16][17].

Regarding the MAC layer implemented in 5G NR, several characteristics have been directly inherited from LTE: the mapping process between logical and transport channels, the multiplexing/demultiplexing of MAC SDUs (Service Data Unit) when required, etc. Moreover, as in LTE, Hybrid Automatic Repeat Request (HARQ) techniques are used for

Fig. 3. Simplified general block diagram of the transceiver architecture

error correction. 5G NR HARQ are error correction techniques based on packet retransmissions schemes. The main difference when compared with 4G is that the timing between data transmission and the HARQ response is flexible. While in 4G timing was fixed to 4ms, in 5G the number of time slots between data transmission and the HARQ response can be dynamically adapted. Undoubtedly, this enables the use of 5G communications for low latency communications.

Another aspect that has been modified in 5G NR PHY is the resource management. As shown in Fig. 2, the smallest data unit that appears in the resource grid is the Resource Element (RE), which, consists of one subcarrier and one OFDM symbol, in frequency and time domain, respectively. However, the Resource Block (RB) concept is not the same as in 4G. In 5G NR, RBs are defined in the frequency domain (12 consecutive subcarriers, independent of the numerology). The time domain definition is flexible and the amount of OFDM symbols can vary. In Fig. 2 a complete time slot has been chosen in the time domain to create the RB (14 OFDM symbols). Moreover, the amount of RBs that can be allocated in a RF channel is also flexible and it varies from 24 to 275 RBs, except for the $\mu = 4$ numerology, where the maximum available RBs is 128. The combination of allocable RBs and the subcarrier spacing, leads to the definition of the minimum and maximum bandwidths (see TABLE III).

IV. 5G-NOMA

In this section, the implications of introducing NOMA in the 5G PHY are presented. First, the general structure is introduced and then, several issues regarding the implementation are explained.

A. General structure

In the first phase of this work, a transceiver has been developed in Matlab. This prototype is fully compliant with the 5G NR Release 15 PHY/MAC standard. A Physical Downlink Shared Channel (PDSCH) has been implemented in the prototype, since 5G NR does not include any specific broadcast channel. Nevertheless, the prototype is compatible with any future broadcast channel that could be introduced in future Releases (Rel'17 or Rel'18). In addition, in order to introduce NOMA in the 5G NR transceiver some

modifications have been done. In Fig. 3, a general block diagram of the overall transceiver is shown. The blocks related to the transmitter are color coded in orange, while receiver blocks are painted in blue.

At the beginning of the transceiver, two independent data flows are created, one per each NOMA layer. The blocks related to UL are located inside the green dashed box, while the blocks related to the LL are inside the red dashed box. First, a Downlink Shared Channel (DL-SCH) transport channel is generated for each layer, which among other issues, its main characteristics is to apply the LDPC coding. Then, the PDSCH generation is applied, where the modulation is applied to the encoded transport blocks.

Once PDSCH are generated for both layers, the NOMA signal ensemble is carried out. Therefore, symbols corresponding to the LL are attenuated by a predefined injection level (g , in Fig. 3). The injection level indicates the relative power distribution between both layers, so g has a real value in between $[0, 1)$, where $g = 0$ results in a single-layer system and $g = 1$ results in a two-layer system with equal power distribution [4]. The injection level can also be represented in dBs ($\Delta = 10 \cdot \log(g)$). Then, the UL and the attenuated LL are added creating the definitive NOMA signal ensemble. After superimposing both layers, the output constellation is normalized. Finally, a precoding is applied and the OFDM signal is generated.

Once the transmitter blocks have finished, the channel model is applied. In this case, two channel model families have been applied: Additive White Gaussian Noise (AWGN) and Tapped Delay Line (TDL) [18]. The first is used as a reference, while the second one is implemented as a more realistic and challenging channel model. TDL channel models are defined for the full frequency range and for non-MIMO transmissions. They are composed by several taps with different delays and amplitudes. Five different channel profiles are defined, where TDL-A, TDL-B and TDL-C represent channel models for Non-Line of Sight (NLOS) conditions and TDL-D and TDL-E are aimed for Line of Sight (LOS) conditions. More details are presented about the parameters of the implemented channel models in section V.

Concerning the receiver side, the OFDM demodulation and the channel estimation modules are carried out first. In this case, perfect channel estimation is assumed. Then, the UL is recovered where demodulation and LDPC decoding is applied

Fig. 4. Resource allocation patterns: (a) generic TDM/FDM, (b) generic LDM, (c) broadcast/unicast convergence solution in TDM/FDM, (d) broadcast/unicast convergence solution in LDM

by implementing PSDCH decoding and DL-SCH decoding, respectively. In these modules, highlighted in a dotted green box, the LL is assumed as additional noise to UL, since the LL has lower power in comparison with the UL noise threshold. Then, in order to recover the LL, a Successive Interference Cancellation (SIC) module has been introduced. This module takes as input the received signal and the regenerated UL. Therefore, the DL-SCH and the PDSCH modules have to be applied again to re-create UL bits. The output of the SIC module is the difference between both signals, which is the received LL. Hence, to obtain the definitive LL, PDSCH decoding and DL-SCH decoding is applied to the output of the SIC module.

In parallel to this process, HARQ retransmission schemes are also implemented. In this case, when the UL data and the LL data are obtained in the DL-SCH decoding module, it is checked if the packet is correctly received. If the packet is successfully received, a new transport block is generated and transmitted. However, if the packet reception is not successful, a retransmission is scheduled by changing the Redundancy Version (RV) value. Moreover, HARQ processes are independently carried out in each layer.

Finally, it is important to highlight the complexity aspects. It is true that introducing NOMA techniques in the 5G NR standard the complexity of the transceiver is increased. However, this complexity drawback does not affect to the UL. In fact, as it can be seen in Fig. 3, the UL decoding chain follows the traditional modules. Therefore, only the LL suffers from extra complexity increase, since it has to face SIC procedures.

B. Frame adaptation layer

Although UL and LL data flows are independently managed, some requirements have to be met. Indeed, when the NOMA signal ensemble is created, the inputs related to both layers must have the same length. That is why, a frame adaptation layer has been developed between the MAC layer and the PHY layer. The following expression is considered the reference of the frame adaptation layer:

$$\# SC_{UL} = \# SC_{LL} \quad (2)$$

where $\# SC$ is the number of subcarriers allocated for the transmission, which is equal for both layers. This parameter defines the amount of coded bits that can be transmitted:

$$\# SC_{UL} = \frac{tx\ bits_{UL}}{m_{UL}} = \frac{tx\ bits_{LL}}{m_{LL}} \quad (3)$$

where $tx\ bits$ is the amount of bits that are introduced in the modulator and m is the modulation index. Finally, the amount of transmitted bits is calculated from the following relation:

$$\# SC_{UL} = \frac{info\ bits_{UL} \cdot CR_{UL}}{m_{UL}} = \frac{info\ bits_{LL} \cdot CR_{LL}}{m_{LL}} \quad (4)$$

where $info\ bits$ is the amount of information bits that are obtained from the MAC layer and CR is the implemented code rate. Assuming a fixed amount of information bits for the UL, the amount of information bits for the LL in each frame is calculated from the following expression:

$$info\ bits_{LL} = \frac{info\ bits_{UL} \cdot CR_{UL} \cdot m_{LL}}{m_{UL} \cdot CR_{LL}} \quad (5)$$

Therefore, the length of the LL packet received from the MAC layer is restricted depending on the MCS (Modulation and Coding Scheme) of each layer and the length of the UL MAC packet length.

In this case, constant frame lengths are used in each simulation. In fact, as a complete time slot is used for each data transmission, the amount of subcarriers allocated for the transmission is defined by the OFDM parameters (SCS and bandwidth). Consequently, the length of the MAC packets is directly decided by defining the transmission modulation and code rate of both layers.

C. Resource allocation

As described in section III, one RB is the minimum data unit that can be allocated in 5G NR. Indeed, this resource

TABLE IV
USE CASES CONFIGURATION

Service	TDMA (50%-50%)			NOMA (I) (IL = -6 dB)			NOMA (II) (IL = -6 dB)			NOMA (III) (IL = -6 dB)		
	MCS	Cap. (Mbps)	SNR _{TH} (dB)	MCS	Cap. (Mbps)	SNR _{TH} (dB)	MCS	Cap. (Mbps)	SNR _{TH} (dB)	MCS	Cap. (Mbps)	SNR _{TH} (dB)
Broadcast	12	30.3	11.1	5	29.5	11	5	29.5	11	5	29.5	11
Unicast	19	51.2	17.5	10	51.4	15.8	12	60.6	18	13	66.4	19.1

allocation technique implies time and frequency domain multiplexing (slots and subcarriers). Therefore, it can be considered a two dimensional multiplexing technique. In Fig. 4(a), an example of a resource allocation pattern is shown. Each color represents the one different service or unicast receiver.

However, if P-NOMA is introduced in the 5G NR resource allocation mechanism, apart from the RBs, another parameter can be taken into account when distributing the resource: the transmitted power. In Fig. 4(b), an example of a resource allocation pattern when P-NOMA is implemented is shown. Again, each color represents a different transmitted service. In this case, inside each RB due to the injection level, more than one service can be delivered. Therefore, if P-NOMA is introduced in 5G NR, a three dimensional resource allocation can be carried out: time, frequency and power. Undoubtedly, this third dimension increases the number of parameters and possible pattern combinations, and, therefore, higher flexibility when applying the resource allocation.

D. Broadcast/Unicast convergence

The resource allocation approach presented in section IV.C presents a new alternative to cover different use cases. In fact, P-NOMA can be used as a mechanism to enable the convergence between broadcast and unicast services in the same RF channel.

On the one hand, in Fig. 4(c) an example is shown of how the broadcast/unicast convergence issue is solved by implementing eMBMS. The dark orange block represents the allocation for the broadcast service, whereas the blue blocks are reserved for different unicast services, where each blue tone represents a specific unicast service. In this case, a 50%-50% time division has been applied for broadcast and unicast service. Moreover, concerning the unicast services, three simultaneous services have been assumed with an equal resource sharing among them. As it can be seen, broadcast and unicast services are multiplexed by using frequency domain multiplexing, although a similar allocation pattern can be obtained if a time domain multiplexing is followed.

On the other hand, in Fig. 4(d) the broadcast/unicast convergence issue is solved by implementing P-NOMA in the 5G NR resource allocation mechanism. As in Fig. 4(c), dark orange block represents the broadcast service and the blue blocks are different unicast services. In this case, broadcast and unicast services are multiplexed using P-NOMA. This means that broadcast and unicast services are sharing the same OFDM symbol and the same subcarriers, but they are separated by power layers. The UL is reserved for the broadcast content, whereas the LL is used for delivering unicast services. Then, in the LL in order to share the resources among the different unicast services frequency domain multiplexing is used. Therefore, the resource

allocation scheme presented in Fig. 4(d) implies LDM + FDM (or TDM) multiplexing scheme concatenation. Comparing Fig. 4(c) and 4(d), the later case certainly provides wider available bandwidth for each service, which achieves capacity gain.

When P-NOMA is used to guarantee the convergence between broadcast and unicast services, the main parameter to configure the overall content distribution is the Injection Level. Therefore, the implemented IL value has a direct impact in the delivered services. For example, if high IL values are selected, higher throughput can be obtained in the UL (or higher reliability). However, as the power reserved for the LL is lower, the available capacity will decrease, and less unicast users could be satisfied. On the other hand, if low ILs are selected in order to enhance the unicast services, the reliability of the UL will be reduced and the coverage area could be noticeably impacted. That is why, a tradeoff has to be assumed between the characteristics of both type of services, broadcast and unicast services.

V. PHY EVALUATION

In this section, the prototype presented in section IV.A is tested over different propagation channels and the results are presented and analyzed.

A. Theoretical approach

Before carrying out simulations, a use case has been defined in order to establish the transmission configurations. In this case, two type services have been designed: broadcast and unicast. The broadcast service configuration has been defined to deliver 4K content. That is why, each broadcast configuration has to offer around 30 Mbps [19]. As correct reception has to be guaranteed by at least 99% of the receivers, reliability is considered a critical aspect. On the other hand, in the case of the unicast services, configurations that allow higher data rates have been used. In fact, 50 Mbps has been established as the reference data rate for unicast services. The main reason is that applications where several users have to share the common resources are the principal target. For this kind of services, the higher the available data rate is, the higher the amount of users that could simultaneously receive the service can be. Some examples of this kind of services are: IoT services for smart traffic management or on demand TV content for mobile receivers.

As described in section IV.D, while broadcast and unicast services have been multiplexed in time and frequency domain with the traditional approach, by using P-NOMA, broadcast services are delivered in the UL and unicast services in the LL. This new approach presents a wider range of possibilities when the configuration is defined. A summary of the use cases are shown in TABLE IV. For each use case configuration, capacity and SNR thresholds (for a bit error rate (BER) value

Fig. 5. Performance BER vs. SNR curves for different channel models: (a) TDL-D with 90ns DS, (b) TDL-D with 360ns DS, (c) TDL-D with 1100ns DS, (d) TDL-E with 90ns DS, (e) TDL-E with 360ns DS, (f) TDL-E with 1100ns DS

of 10^{-6}) are presented. The capacity values are calculated using a 20 MHz bandwidth channel. The SNR thresholds simulations are based on an AWGN channel.

First, the TDMA based configuration is described. In order to achieve the target data rates, MCS 12 and MCS 19 (according to Table 5.1.3.1-2 in [20]) have to be implemented for broadcast and unicast services, respectively. Then, in the case of the P-NOMA based cases, as gains in the LL are targeted, UL values with similar implications in comparison with TDMA have been defined.

Regarding the LL, three different configurations have been defined in order to analyze three different situations. In the first case, NOMA (I), a very similar capacity value has been selected to obtain reliability gains. Indeed, 1.7 dB are obtained. The second case, NOMA (II), has similar reliability values (a difference of 0.5 dB) and more than 9 Mbps of capacity gain. Finally, the third case, NOMA (III), offers a very high capacity gain (more than 15 Mbps) due to assuming some reliability penalization (1.6 dB). In each NOMA based configuration the injection level applied has been -6 dB.

It is also important to highlight that is almost impossible to make a completely exact comparison between both technologies. Indeed, the numerology of 5G NR does not easily provide combinations to replicate the same data rate values for P-NOMA configurations and TDMA. That is why, reliability and capacity values shown in TABLE IV are not exactly the same for TDMA and P-NOMA technologies.

B. Simulation results

Once a preliminary analysis based on the AWGN channel has been carried out, more simulations have been performed over different propagation channels in order to widen the results.

Concerning the wireless propagation channel, TDL-D and TDL-E profiles have been implemented. In both cases, the LOS condition is included. Additionally, three different delay spread (DS) values have been simulated for each channel model: 90ns, 360 ns and 1100ns. Those values have been selected because they are aligned with short-, normal- and long-delay profiles for an urban environment [18].

Results obtained with the developed transceiver over the detailed channels are presented in Fig. 5. Following those graphics, a comparison can be made between P-NOMA and TDMA multiplexing schemes performance. In each plot, the y-axis represents the BER, whereas the x-axis is the SNR value in dB.

From a general perspective, each transmission configuration shows a similar performance over the different channels. In comparison with the AWGN channel, the performance is deteriorated between 0.3 dB and 2 dB. The short-delay and the normal-delay profiles, present very similar results in both cases. It should be highlighted, however, that the long-delay profile channels have stronger negative effects on the received signal and the required SNR thresholds are higher. In fact, the

TABLE V
RELIABILITY/CAPACITY GAIN ANALYSIS OF THE LL (UNICAST SERVICES)

Metric	NOMA (I)	NOMA (II)	NOMA (III)
TDL-D 90 ns	1.7	-0.4	-1.7
TDL-E 90 ns	1.7	-0.6	-1.6
SNR _{TH} Gain (dB)			
TDL-D 360 ns	1.8	-0.5	-1.5
TDL-E 360 ns	1.7	-0.4	-1.6
TDL-D 1100 ns	1.8	-0.4	-1.5
TDL-E 1100 ns	2.0	-0.2	-1.5
Capacity Gain (Mbps)	0.2	9.4	15.2
Gain in IoT case (Users)	1	47	76
Gain in Mobile Video case (Users)	0	5	8

TDL-E channel model is even more challenging in long-delay conditions than the TDL-D.

As expected, services oriented to fixed receivers (TDMA (I) and NOMA (UL)) show a very similar reliability performance. In fact, the difference between both cases, in terms of required SNR threshold for a BER value of 10^{-6} , is around 0.1 dB. However, the behavior of the BER vs SNR curve is not identical in both cases. While the TDMA case presents a very pronounced decrease, the UL case has a slower decrease. This difference is due to the NOMA configuration. The effective SNR value for the UL is close to 6 dB, due to the injection level. This value is very close to the SNR threshold required to decode this configuration in the single layer mode and, in consequence, the UL is not able to offer a fast decrease. Nevertheless, this problem is solved by increasing the injection value. In that case, the SNR value required to obtain the LL service is higher. Therefore, when deciding the injection level value, a tradeoff has to be assumed between the convergence of the UL and the SNR required in the LL.

Regarding the performance in the case of mobile receivers (TDMA (II) and LL), the advantages of the different configurations presented in TABLE IV are confirmed. In TABLE V, an in-depth analysis is carried out in terms of capacity and reliability for the unicast services, which are delivered in the LL in the case of P-NOMA. Each of the metrics presented in TABLE V, demonstrates the gain of P-NOMA over the equivalent TDMA configuration. The SNR threshold gain has very little variation over the different channels. As expected, the first P-NOMA configuration presents a minimum reliability gain of 1.7 dB by maintaining almost equal the capacity. The second case offers 9.4 Mbps of capacity gain by assuming a similar reliability performance (0.6 dB of deterioration on the worst case). Finally, in the third case the capacity gain is maximized, presenting 15.2 Mbps more than the TDMA case, which represents a 30% of capacity gain. The main drawback of this solution is that up to 1.7 dB of SNR deterioration has to be assumed. Overall, these P-NOMA cases, presents a wide range of possible selections when configuring the transmission system.

TABLE V presents a capacity gain comparison in terms of satisfied users for different potential application cases: IoT services and mobile video delivery. For the first one, the characteristics defined in the Release 13 (Narrow Band IoT LTE, NB-IoT LTE) have been taken into account, where a maximum data rate of 200 kbps per user in downlink channels is established [21]. For the second use case, where unicast users will receive HD video content in their mobile or portable

TABLE VI
SIMULATION PARAMETERS

Parameter	Value
Center Frequency	2 GHz
Tx Power	44 dBm
Distance attenuation	$128.1 + 37.6 \cdot \log(d)$
Type of nodes	Fixed, pedestrians, cars
Speed	Fixed: 0 km/h
	Pedestrians: 3 km/h
	Cars: 30, 50 km/h
Number of Nodes	Fixed: 75
	Pedestrians: 15
	Cars: 10
Mobility type	Fixed: Static
	Pedestrians: RWP
	Cars: Linear
Coverage area	500 m
Tx configuration (TDMA)	Broadcast: MCS12
	Unicast: MCS19
Tx configuration (NOMA)	Time division: 50%-50%
	Broadcast: MCS5
	Unicast: MCS10, 12, 13
	Injection Level: -6 dB
Delay Spread	90, 360, 1100 ns
Noise Power	-90 dBm
Noise Figure	9 dB
Channel model	TDL-D, TDL-E
Simulated seeds	25
Simulation time	5 min per seed

devices, a minimum data rate of 2 Mbps has been assumed [22]. Therefore, from the capacity calculations presented in TABLE V, in TDMA unicast configuration proposal, 256 users could be connected in the IoT case and 25 in the mobile video content delivery case. As it has been demonstrated, P-NOMA configurations increase considerably the amount of possible users. The greatest increases appear in NOMA (III) case, where up to 76 IoT devices could be added and 8 mobile video devices more could be supported.

VI. NETWORK SIMULATION

The objective of this section is to test the performance of the proposed solution in a realistic network environment, taking into account MAC layer techniques and compare the performance with the equivalent traditional TDMA solutions.

A. Simulation methodology

In order to evaluate the developed transceiver in a network environment, a packet level simulator is required. In this case, the evaluation performance has been carried out in an upgraded OMNeT++ [23]. This network simulation tool is composed of both PHY and MAC layers for each of the implemented transmitters and receivers.

On the one hand, the PHY layer module facilitates the selection of the parameters that define the waveform, such as the subcarrier spacing. In addition, the transmission parameters have to be configured (modulation and code rate). PHY performance curves presented in the previous sections are used to estimate the transmission success. For each one of the received packets, the current SNR value of the receiver is used to determine the packet error rate (PER) according to the performance curves. The transformation from BER to PER is carried out following the technique presented in [24]. On the

TABLE VII
NETWORK LEVEL RELIABILITY/LATENCY ANALYSIS

User Type	PER				Mean Latency (μ s)			
	TDMA	NOMA (I)	NOMA (II)	NOMA (III)	TDMA	NOMA (I)	NOMA (II)	NOMA (III)
Fixed (UL)	$3.75 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$3.75 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$3.75 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$3.75 \cdot 10^{-5}$	-	-	-	-
Pedestrian (LL)	$6.13 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$3.66 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$7.14 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$9.71 \cdot 10^{-2}$	5.02	3.20	5.08	6.37
Car (LL)	$2.98 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$1.75 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$3.47 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$4.69 \cdot 10^{-2}$	28.18	21.85	30.07	34.25
Total	$1.22 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$7.26 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.42 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$1.93 \cdot 10^{-2}$	14.29	10.66	15.08	17.52

other hand, concerning the MAC layer, HARQ type retransmission schemes are implemented.

Regarding the network architecture and the implemented scenario, the channel model module and the mobility module are the most relevant parts of the simulated model. The former is in charge of defining the characteristics of the channel model, such as the maximum Doppler frequency, the delay spread value or the implemented channel profile (TDL-D or TDL-E). Indeed, this module is closely related with the user type, since, while the channel for fixed receiver is considered almost constant, the channel affecting the receiver with the highest mobility will show a fastest change. This concept is also taken into account by the mobility model module, which takes care of detailing how the receiver is moving. Different mobility models are available in OMNeT++ for different type of receivers. However, to introduce the time variability characteristics of the channel models in the simulator, they have been previously simulated in Matlab.

B. Use case definition

In this work, an urban environment has been emulated in OMNeT++, where different types of receivers with different service requirements coexist in the same cell. Three groups of users have been defined: fixed receivers, low-speed pedestrian receivers and car-mounted receivers. The first group of users represents traditional broadcast receivers, based on roof top antenna reception. However, pedestrian and car-mounted receivers are aimed to more challenge data applications, e.g., on demand video content. Therefore, this network architecture emulates a real scenario where a convergence application is required in order to guarantee the correct reception of traditional broadcast systems and different unicast services.

In each simulation, a total number of 100 devices have been included. Specifically, 75 fixed receivers have been assumed inside each cell, 15 pedestrians and 10 car-mounted user devices. Due to the different receiver characteristics, different mobility models have been designed for each receiver family. Fixed receivers have a static model, whereas pedestrians have been allocated a concrete walker mobility type referred as Random Way Point (RWP) [25]. In the case of cars, considering the characteristics of city roads, a linear mobility type has been used. Speed is also specified for each receiver. In this case, pedestrian receivers walk inside the cell with a mean speed of 3 km/h and the car receivers vary their speed between 30-50 km/h.

The parameters values are critical when defining the propagation attenuation suffered by the transmitted signal. In fact, those parameters define the propagation channel. In this case, all the channel combinations presented in Fig. 5 have been considered. Moreover, each channel model varies with a specific Doppler frequency value depending on the speed of the receiver.

The rest of the network simulation parameters are gathered in TABLE VI.

C. Results

The evaluation of the proposed NOMA-based 5G model has been based on three key parameter indicators (KPIs): reliability, latency and throughput. First, to measure the reliability, PER is used as a metric. Second, the mean latency value is evaluated. The implemented deterministic grid design limits the possible latency values. Therefore, the latency measured at the receiver is bounded for a finite number of possibilities. In consequence, the mean latency is used instead of the maximum latency, because even if they are not values that will appear in a real case, it is possible to quantify the difference of the latency performance in an objective way. In this case, the latency generated in the SIC module is not taken into account. Finally, for the throughput, two metrics are used: normalized data reception index (NDRI) and effective throughput. The NDRI indicates the relation between the amount of information received and the maximum information rate that could be received in the error free case. Moreover, not only error packets reduce the NDRI value, also the delivered retransmissions, since using retransmissions, the overall received capacity is decreased because the same content is repeatedly transmitted. This parameter is measured in percentage data. The following expression has been used to calculate the NDRI:

$$NDRI (\%) = \frac{\text{correct packets}}{\text{correct packets} + \text{retx attempts}} \cdot 100 \quad (6)$$

where, *retx attempts* are the total number of retransmissions that have been carried out for each node. On the other hand, the effective throughput represents the useful received capacity. This parameter also takes into account the number of retransmissions that have been implemented by combing the NDRI with the transmitted capacity:

$$\text{eff. throughput (Mbps)} = \frac{NDRI \cdot \text{tx capacity}}{100} \quad (7)$$

In TABLE VII, a dual comparison is presented between P-NOMA-based and TDMA-based configurations in reliability and latency terms. Regarding the fixed receivers, as expected, the same PER values are obtained in each case due to the configurations that have been applied. Latency cannot be measured in the case of fixed receivers. Being the service a broadcast type service, there is no uplink to transmit the feedback and, so, retransmissions cannot be implemented. In the case of mobile receivers, in general, the best reliability results are obtained in the NOMA (I) case, which is designed aiming to improve the reliability. The packet error rate is

Fig. 6. Network level throughput analysis of the LL (unicast services)

reduced by 40%. As expected, NOMA (II) and NOMA (III) cases present worse PER values in comparison with TDMA configuration. If reliability is compared for the user type, the best results appear for fixed users because of the low SNR threshold required. On the other hand, for the mobile receivers, better results appear in the case of cars than in pedestrians. This effect is closely related with the channel affecting each receiver type. In the case of cars, as they are moving faster than pedestrians, their Doppler frequency is higher and, therefore, the channel response varies faster. Undoubtedly, in this situation, time-based retransmissions work better than in the case of pedestrians, where the channel response changes slower.

Similar conclusions can be obtained from mean latency values in TABLE VII. The lowest latency values appear in NOMA (I) because of the reliability that the configuration offers. However, in this case, car receivers have higher mean latency values than pedestrians. High latency values indicate that packets are more frequently received in the retransmissions slots than in cases with low latency. Therefore, the combination of PER and latency results confirms that retransmissions are more effective in the case of cars, while in the case of pedestrians they have lower effectivity rate.

Concerning the received throughput, a summary graphic is plotted in Fig. 6. Only results of mobile receivers are presented in this graphic because fixed receivers present almost identical results. Regarding the NDRI results, the behavior that can be denoted is comparable to the behavior presented in the PER values. The best results are obtained in the NOMA (I) case, which are very close to 90%. The worst results are in the case of NOMA (III), and NOMA (II) and TDMA configurations offer similar NDRI results. Nevertheless, in the case of the effective throughput results, the behavior is completely different. TDMA configuration offers the worst results (below 1.8 Mbps/user), while NOMA cases increment the effective throughput when increasing the implemented MCS. The difference between the worst and the best cases is an increment of 21.8%. These results indicate that the reliability decrease is compensated by transmitting with a higher capacity configuration.

VII. FUTURE WORK

Although interesting results have been presented in this work, taking into account that this is the first full P-NOMA-based 5G NR transceiver proposal and evaluation, there are still some future works in the horizon that could bring about complementary works.

On the one hand, concerning the stack protocol, upper layers could be taken into account for future developments. For example, if the IP-layer is included in addition to the proposed service level convergence, IP-based convergence could also be proposed. In this case, 5G NR could be complemented with another technology, such as ATSC 3.0 or DVB-T2.

On the other hand, more simulations will be carried out to evaluate a wider range of possible scenarios. In this case, the objective will be to measure the gain that can be obtained by adding P-NOMA in 5G NR in different environments. As highlighted in section V.B, one of the proposed NOMA configurations offers a considerable reliability gain that could be transformed in an improvement of the coverage area. Therefore, similar configurations will be proposed to be used in rural areas or isolated small areas with limitations on the service quality.

Finally, different specific applications could be proposed at MAC or resource allocation layer in order to complement this solution. A good alternative will be to propose a novel subgrouping technique, as the one proposed in [13], based on the architecture proposed in this work.

VIII. CONCLUSIONS

A P-NOMA-based 5G NR transceiver has been designed, presented and evaluated at PHY/MAC level as a mechanism to guarantee the convergence between broadcast and unicast services. Besides the design and implementation transceiver architecture, the main implications that have to be taken into account have been presented. In addition to that, two different evaluating techniques have been developed over two completely different simulation tools to obtain various perspectives.

In the PHY layer analysis, different NOMA-based configurations have been defined in order to cover a specific service convergence use case. Based on those configurations, possible reliability and/or capacity gains were foreseen first, and then, they were confirmed by using six different channel models. In the case of the capacity gain, depending on the configuration used, up to 76 IoT receivers could be added to the network and 8 mobile video receivers.

On the other hand, in the network simulation tool, the configurations presented before have been implemented in a realistic network environment. Reliability, latency and throughput have been evaluated by using different metrics. Reliability and latency measurements indicate that the most appropriate configuration for those terms for the unicast services is NOMA (I). However, from the capacity perspective, NOMA (III) is the best solution because it offers the highest capacity per user rate. Moreover, HARQ retransmission schemes appear to be more effective when the receivers are moving faster, due to the higher channel response variance.

All in all, based on the obtained results, NOMA can be considered as a competitive alternative, even better than time based solutions, for offering broadcast/unicast convergence.

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